

STAGES AND CONTENT OF DEVELOPING TEAMWORK SKILLS OF STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15312335>

Abstract. *The given article reflects on the fact that mutual joint action is one of the main ways to activate the self-development and manifestation of the student, the ability and opportunities of students are more manifested in the process of collaborative activities, by complementing each other, they can achieve a qualitatively new level of development, the stages and content of the development.*

Keywords: *collaborative, communicative, creative thinking, critical (critical) thinking, dating stage, task setting stage, stage of organizing active communication, stage of organizing practical projects, stage of reflection.*

INTRODUCTION

The rapid implementation of education reforms in our country, ensuring the strong interconnection between the stages of continuous education, teaching students in line with the new demands of society, and enriching teaching methodologies with global experiences, is being dynamically carried out. In this regard, the political processes related to primary education, foreign programs, and experiences specifically aimed at primary education create a need to organize research in this area.

Definitely, primary education is the most crucial stage in the formation of an individual. During this period, as the child subconsciously starts to comprehend the world, lay the foundation for imagination and knowledge, it demands delicate attention. It is at this stage that the child creates their "learner's identity," develops interest and affection for school and learning, and begins to gather strength for future academic achievements. This, therefore, requires a serious approach to the ideological, educational, and enlightening level of textbooks as a continuous and complex issue in modern pedagogy.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Collaborative activities are one of the main methods to activate students' self-development and self-expression. In the process of cooperative activities, students' abilities and opportunities are more prominently revealed. By complementing each other, they reach a qualitatively new level of development.

D.B. Elkonin and V.V. Davydov state that all forms of interpersonal relations at school have a general character and are governed not only by "child-adult" relations but also by "child-child" interactions. Therefore, the effectiveness of the norm of harmonious behavior is not only reflected in the integrity of the class but also requires working in small groups, which simultaneously demonstrates group emotional support.

A.A. Ivin, in his scientific research, emphasizes that the relationships with peers differ from the "child-adult" relationships, as they primarily ensure equality. Communication with peers provides students with the opportunity to engage in interactions based on mutual respect, as well as to critically reflect on others' words and actions independently of adults' views and desires. To

achieve this, students must develop the ability to understand, evaluate, accept, or reject others' perspectives, and most importantly, possess and defend their own personal views and beliefs, which are distinct from others.

American psychologist J. Moreno proposed a method for determining interpersonal preferences within groups and a technique for recording emotional preferences. He called this method sociometry. Sociometry allows for the identification of the quantitative norms of preference, indifference, or aversion that manifest among group members during collaborative activities. German researcher V. Myode developed a program for group cooperation, which, at first glance, seemed to focus on studying cognitive processes in individuals. However, the actual goal was to examine the influence of the group on individual psychological activity. In his experiments, conducted with groups of 2-3 people up to 16 individuals, he used specialized equipment to examine the effects of muscle activity, endurance, sensitivity, attention, memory, and various associations, first in isolation and later in group settings.

Russian pedagogue A.S. Makarenko placed great emphasis on the internal aspects of group relationships. He identified the following key characteristics formed within a group:

- Constant vigilance and readiness for activity among the students;
- Understanding the essence of the group's values and recognizing one's own worth based on pride in being part of the group;
- Friendly unity among group members;
- Friendly relations with each member of the group;
- Active participation that leads to organized, productive efforts;
- The ability to manage one's own emotions and words.

Certainly, pedagogical and psychological research has shown that the methodology of working in groups enhances students' activity, broadens their thinking processes, and fosters creativity. The facts uncovered in research confirm that through interactive learning activities, students not only deepen their academic knowledge but also develop interpersonal relationships, social integration, and independent thinking skills. Therefore, the skills formed through group work lay the foundation for students' successful actions in real-life situations, the assumption of various social roles, and the performance of leadership tasks in their future professional careers. The research used methods such as observation, direct interviews, surveys, and pedagogical experiments.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The new principle, the 4K approach, which is starting to be applied in elementary schools, includes four principles in its name. The 4K principle ensures the development of students in many areas such as creativity, critical thinking, communication, and collaboration, not limiting them to just one field. These skills help students to succeed not only in the educational process but also in life. Each element of the 4K principle helps students develop abilities necessary for fully utilizing their potential, such as learning relationships, exchanging ideas, and solving problems.

- **Collaboration:** The textbooks are designed to help develop students' ability to work in teams. This assists students in learning collaboration, exchanging ideas effectively, and supporting each other.
- **Communication:** Students learn to express their ideas clearly and concisely, listen to others, understand them, and use language effectively to convey information.

- **Creative Thinking:** Students learn to apply new approaches to achieve their goals, develop innovative solutions, and have the skills to solve creative problems.
- **Critical Thinking:** This methodology helps students develop the ability to critically evaluate information, form their own opinions and reflections. Students learn to approach problems from an analytical perspective and develop their viewpoints based on logical thinking.

Before implementing the new innovative approach in Uzbekistan schools, foreign experiences were also studied. Countries with advanced education systems such as Singapore, China, England, Finland, and Estonia focus primarily on developing 21st-century skills in students, including the 4K principles. The results of this new innovative approach can be seen in the growth of students' worldviews and thinking. In the portrait of a 21st-century student, 21st-century skills should be present. The main goal of applying the innovative approach is the same. Moreover, the main goal of education is not only to give students knowledge but also to teach them to apply the knowledge they have gained in life.

The importance of developing teamwork skills in elementary grades is significant as it is the first stage of their educational journey, and it is during this period that their ability to work in teams is developed.

Developing students' teamwork skills is a complex and step-by-step process that requires implementation, which develops not only students' academic knowledge but also their social, communicative, and problem-solving abilities. This process starts with introducing students to group activities for the first time and continues until they gain practical experience and move on to independent collaboration.

Let's look at the stages of developing teamwork skills in elementary school students and their description:

Stages	Description	Activities	Results
1. Introduction stage	This stage is aimed at introducing students to the team environment for the first time. The goal is to foster mutual acquaintance, respect, and trust among the students. In this way, a foundation for healthy communication and cooperation within the team is established.	Through group games and "introduction" activities (such as "Name Chain" or "Blindfolding"), students get to know each other better. Simple group discussions and collaborative tasks (such as drawing a picture together or creating a short story) are organized. Through interactive activities, students begin to engage in conversations, gradually creating a trustworthy	A sense of mutual trust and respect is developed among the students. The necessary foundations for free exchange of ideas and communication within the team are solidified. Positive psychological preparation for future group activities is created.

		communication environment.	
2. Setting tasks stage	In this stage, students learn to define tasks and roles within the group. Each student's personal abilities, talents, and interests are taken into account, so that every member of the group knows their specific responsibilities.	An open discussion is held within the group, and roles (such as leader, writer, timekeeper, materials preparer, etc.) are assigned. Small tasks and role-playing games related to the roles are organized. The teacher and students collaboratively test the roles and evaluate their effectiveness.	Each student clearly understands their role in the team and feels a sense of responsibility. Tasks within the group are distributed fairly and effectively, strengthening mutual trust and collaboration. Students are encouraged to develop their abilities, and skills for active participation in teamwork are formed.
3. Organization of active communication stage	In this stage, students develop skills for establishing effective communication and collaboratively solving emerging problems. This process includes exchanging ideas, listening, and constructive criticism among team members.	Problem-solving tasks are tackled as a group, with brainstorming sessions and small debates organized. Role-playing games and simulations are used to test communication and problem-solving methods in various situations. The teacher observes the group's activities and provides advice on how to resolve conflicts in a constructive manner.	Students learn to express their opinions freely and listen to others' perspectives. Methods for solving group problems, resolving conflicts, and constructive communication are developed. Through effective communication, collaboration and trust among group members are further strengthened.
4. Organizing practical projects stage	In this stage, students consolidate the collective skills they have learned through practical activities, creative projects, and adapting to real-life	Creative projects are prepared in groups, role-playing games, small theatrical skits, and team tasks are carried out. Within the framework of practical tasks,	Students will have the opportunity to apply their theoretical knowledge in practice. Through teamwork, creativity, initiative, and a sense of responsibility are

	<p>situations. This helps them further develop their knowledge and social abilities.</p>	<p>students engage in activities such as planning, completing tasks, and presenting results in front of the class.</p> <p>During the projects, students exchange ideas, discuss experiences, and evaluate results.</p>	<p>further strengthened.</p> <p>Project-based activities significantly improve students' academic and social outcomes.</p>
5. Reflection stage	<p>This stage focuses on evaluating and analyzing the process of group activities by both students and the teacher. The goal is to analyze collaboration, communication, problem-solving, and overall results, and to develop improvement strategies for future activities.</p>	<p>Reflection sessions are organized within the group for self-assessment and to analyze the students' own activities. Activity results are determined through feedback provided by the teacher, evaluation grids, and group discussions. Students will have the opportunity to identify their strengths and weaknesses and express their thoughts on how to work more effectively in the future.</p>	<p>Students will analyze the collaborative process, which will help them deepen their understanding of their potential and teamwork skills.</p> <p>Strong strategies for improving the effectiveness of future group work will be developed. In addition, students will cultivate self-awareness, a desire for self-improvement, and the ability to engage in constructive feedback and reflection.</p>

Through these stages, students gradually develop teamwork skills. Each stage contributes significantly to their personal, social, and academic development with specific tasks, activities, and outcomes. As a result, students become more effective, responsible, and creative in their collaborative efforts.

The process of developing teamwork skills in students is a unified, continuous, and complementary sequence of stages, each of which is aimed at forming and strengthening a culture of teamwork. At the beginning of this process, students enter a collaborative work environment where it is essential for them to get to know each other and build mutual trust. In this stage, the teacher uses interactive games, icebreaker activities, and simple group tasks to help students understand the benefits of working in teams. The goal is for students to not only get to know each other but also to learn to respect each other's opinions and communicate openly and confidently. In doing so, their personal qualities responsibility, empathy, and a spirit of collaboration are strengthened.

In the next stage of the process, students learn to identify roles and distribute tasks within the team. Each student's personal strengths, skills, and interests are taken into account, and based on this, clear roles are assigned within the group. For example, some may become the team leader, others may take on writing, time management, or material preparation responsibilities. This stage helps students understand their position within the team, feel personal responsibility, and prepare for tackling more complex tasks together in the future. By clearly knowing their roles and responsibilities, students will learn to work effectively as a team and solve problems collaboratively.

In the next stage, students will develop skills in active communication, exchanging ideas, and solving problems through constructive criticism. During this process, the teacher guides students through observations and instructions, showing them how to communicate effectively, express their opinions openly, and listen to others when tackling problem-solving tasks. Through interactive discussions, brainstorming sessions, role-playing, and simulation exercises, students will not only grasp theoretical knowledge but also learn to apply it in practice. In this way, they strengthen their ability to resolve conflicts that may arise in team activities constructively, make joint decisions, and communicate effectively by providing mutual support.

In the next phase of the process, students will test their theoretical knowledge through practical activities. This stage involves activities such as creative projects, group tasks, role-playing, and small theater performances. During these activities, students will develop skills such as planning, dividing tasks, monitoring the workflow, and presenting the results in front of the class. Through practical assignments, they will learn to collaborate to find creative solutions, take initiative, and demonstrate their personal abilities. This process also encourages students to evaluate the results of teamwork and develop strategies for working even more effectively in the future based on those evaluations.

In the final stage of the process, students and the teacher together evaluate, analyze, and reflect on the process of team activities to achieve the results. In this phase, students assess their own activities, task distribution, communication methods, and problem-solving processes. Through self-awareness and reflection, they identify areas for improvement in their future work. The teacher, through feedback, assessment charts, and group discussions, analyzes the strengths and weaknesses of the team activity and develops effective strategies for future lessons. This stage also contributes to the students' personal and social development, as well as the enhancement of their communication and constructive feedback skills.

CONCLUSIONS. By summarizing it should be suggested that overall, this continuous process serves not only to strengthen students' team working skills but also to develop them in a deeper and more comprehensive manner. Beginning with mutual trust and acquaintance, and progressing through role identification, active communication, and problem-solving, the practical activities and final reflection stages further develop students' personal potential, creative thinking, and team collaboration culture. As a result, students are shaped to become individuals who, in the future, will not only achieve academic success but also engage in effective cooperation, with a responsible and creative approach to social life.

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